

RECIPE TO MAKE A MULTI DIVERSITY TEAM TO SUCCEED IN COMPLEX PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

With every change in project environment and climate, consistent and quality delivery is always a challenge. This is because every such change affects the core of project management – Project Resource management- that ripples down into other areas of project management such as project schedule management and project cost management. The core competency needed for the every delivery resides with the team. When such a team in hand consists of members belonging to different generation cohorts, optimized delivery gets more challenging. It is more challenging for project managers who need to consider the responses of every generation cohort in the team and take stable decisions. It could get very demanding for project managers if they fail to understand the difference in team's response for the same problem or any external stimuli. It is very important thus to understand the work variables that critically influence the behavior of a particular team cohort to better interpret and take intelligent and innovative decisions especially in complex projects. The concept of the paper is directed towards the study of project outcomes that influence generation cohorts and induce multi-generational diversity concerns within a complex project. The objective of this paper is to exhibit the project outcomes influenced by the work variables of cohorts and understand how the cohorts would respond to them. An initial independent examination into the characteristics of the generation cohorts and work variables was done. A detailed listing of work variables followed by classifying them on basis of their impact was done. The work variables are classified as Organizational, Group and Individual variables, which are highly influenced by mutigenerational diversity. This paper intends to bring out the study done on the group category of work variables, which have affected the manner in which the team cohorts had reacted thereby inducing a sequel of events.

The researcher collected data from secondary sources and through questionnaires among IT Project managers of large, medium and small projects and arrived at the identification of the work variables that are influenced by multigenerational diversity. The findings of this paper would aid to profile the primary task of a project manager to understand how the complex project team can resource charted based on generations. It also suggests how to respond to each cohort which will lead to innovative project management solutions. When project managers attempt to innovate ideas during such turbulences, there is always a scope of integrating and coping better with external environments' researcher has attempted to provide a systemic view of these variables and the attempted to understand the effects of such variables on project performance. This would enable project managers to ensure that no issues within the team would derail the core objective of the project. The finding will also suggest how Multigenerational Diversity at work place is to be managed effectively so that projects run successfully with in its scope, schedule and cost constraints.

Keywords: Multigenerational Diversity, Group Variables, Generational cohorts, innovative ideas, constraints

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INTRODUCTION

IT projects of today rule every business domain to such extent that every industry feels itself challenged if the IT transformation does not occur from within. Heavy digitization and digital transformation projects across various domains, be it Hi Tech, Utilities, Retail, Energy or Manufacturing have found themselves swept by the digital transformation wave. This has given rise to the inception of large and complex Due to high degree of delivery agency some of the IT projects even fail to understand and comprehend the initial objectives lined for the project. Such failures are hard to be justified and mitigated for complex projects as they can lead to financial death of big organizations for whom the project is undertaken.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

With more than four generations working in a project and the heaviness of automation and technology pressing hard, managers need to study the diversity impacts in a project and devise techniques to handle complex projects effectively. The question in hand is how the new wave of digital transformation and disruption handle the events triggered by multigenerational diversity. Diversity in Workplace is an issue that keeps rumbling like a dormant volcano and that organizations need to be alert enough and deploy strategies to effectively utilize the power of workplace diversity.

Understanding in the impacts of Diversity on organizational outcomes especially for complex projects is very pivotal for sustainability. The paper attempts to study the Differences in Generational Cohorts responses towards Project Performance Management considering Complexity of the Project.

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Workplaces are becoming increasingly age diverse, and the incidence of older employees reporting to younger managers is increasing. One of the biggest challenges for organizations in the coming years will be the retirement of older workers and their replacement with the younger workers. Hence organizations have to adopt effective strategies to recruit, mentor and retain the younger generation entering the work space. (Jean M. Twenge, 2010)

LITERATURE REVIEW

Much of the work on generations has been based on observation rather than large-scale empirical findings, and very little academic research has been done on the characteristics and expectations of generations and their implications for the workplace. Although significant attention has been given to cultural and gender diversity, the literature has produced scant evidence regarding the impact of age diversity on HRM policy and practices.

Jeta, Fanta and Reidl, Rene have stated that human factors are very critical for project success especially for Information Systems and Information Technology Literature. (Riedl, 2012). They had scientifically investigated that the human factors in a typical IT Team are influenced by power, organizational politics etc.

Harvey, Micahel (Michael Harvey, 9 September 2005), have found that for organizations to scale up delivery, they need to virtualize their teams as well. They have circled down to four critical capitals which are motivation centric and focused around human, social, political and cross cultural.

(Abyad, 2017) has detailed on the effect of Globalization on Project Management which is based on Political, cultural and economic factors which are influenced by intercultural communications, sociability etc which are based on generational diversity issues.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A descriptive quantitative approach is followed to exemplify the multi generational factors affecting project management and to identify the factors influencing Cost Performance and Schedule performance indices. Long,et.al(2019)¹ explain on why Project complexity is a contributing factor to project performance. Study has indicated that project complexity is positively correlated with Project schedule and negatively correlated with resource allocation. The findings of this study indicate the impact of project complexity on schedule performance and how this can be mimised by optimal resource allocation. It is suggested that project complexity be identified at the early stage of the project itself. Infact project managers should early on identify if the complexity is descriptive or perceived.

The below null Hypotheses is proposed to be analysed and check if the results are significant

H₀: Project Complexity does not have an impact on project performance

¹ Long D. Nguyena, Long Le-Hoaib, Dai Q. Tranc, Chau N. Dangd and Chau V. Nguyene, Effect of project complexity on cost and schedule performance in transportation projects, CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMICS 2019, VOL. 37, NO. 7, 384–399

H a: Project Complexity does have an impact on project performance

Primary data for the research was collected using a web-based structured self- administered questionnaire. All the measurement items in the developed questionnaire, which measured the constructs were adopted from previous research studies and modified to suit the research. One way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is applied to ascertain the difference between the project outcomes when multiple generations constitute the project team of varying complexity

Analysis

The below section attempts to analyze the Differences in Generational Cohorts responses towards Project Performance Management considering Complexity of the Project using ANOVA Technique

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Project Scope Management	A shift in an organization's priorities impacted the progress of a project	Between Groups	2.495	2	1.248	1.271	.282
		Within Groups	374.995	382	.982		
		Total	377.491	384			
Project Scope Management	Change in Scope of the project objectives had an impact on the project health	Between Groups	1.320	2	.660	.787	.456
		Within Groups	320.513	382	.839		
		Total	321.834	384			
Project Scope Management	The requirements were not gathered with customer empathy	Between Groups	3.143	2	1.572	1.342	.263
		Within Groups	445.102	380	1.171		
		Total	448.245	382			
Project Stakeholder Management	Key Stakeholders were not given enough clarity on the Project goals and the customer's vision of the project.	Between Groups	3.965	2	1.982	1.656	.192
		Within Groups	453.774	379	1.197		
		Total	457.738	381			
Project Communication Management	Gap in communication within the project team and with stakeholders affected project health and progress	Between Groups	1.991	2	.996	.984	.375
		Within Groups	385.665	381	1.012		
		Total	387.656	383			
Project Risk Management	Insufficient Risk and process improvement analysis	Between Groups	.432	2	.216	.206	.814
		Within Groups	398.962	380	1.050		
		Total	399.394	382			
Project Risk Management	Failure of Risk Identification during the early stages of the project.	Between Groups	.686	2	.343	.314	.731
		Within Groups	415.814	381	1.091		
		Total	416.500	383			
Project Schedule Management	Incorrect resource planning leading to delays	Between Groups	2.016	2	1.008	.864	.422
		Within Groups	444.669	381	1.167		
		Total	446.685	383			
Project Human Resource Management	Ad Hoc coverage by overloading certain resources to overcome team procrastination	Between Groups	1.324	2	.662	.491	.612
		Within Groups	508.347	377	1.348		
		Total	509.671	379			
Project Stakeholder Management	Recurrivise follow up and poor implementation of the feedback provided in team meetings	Between Groups	.956	2	.478	.451	.637
		Within Groups	402.756	380	1.060		
		Total	403.713	382			
Project Stakeholder Management	Delayed guidance and support from project stakeholders (managers, sponsors, SME etc)	Between Groups	5.919	2	2.959	2.983	.052
		Within Groups	379.939	383	.992		
		Total	385.858	385			
Project Communication Management	Unprofessional resolution of project issues	Between Groups	3.984	2	1.992	1.569	.210
		Within Groups	483.742	381	1.270		

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		Total	487.727	383			
Project Human Resource Management	Inability of team to upskill competency	Between Groups	.611	2	.305	.259	.772
		Within Groups	448.475	380	1.180		
		Total	449.086	382			

From the above table it is found that there is no significant impact due to any of the above listed factors. Hence when complexity of the project and the factors considered for project performance as mentioned above are not significantly impacting each other.

However the below factors listed in the below table have significance value less than 0.05 and hence it is derived that there will be a significant impact on project performance when considered along with complexity. Tukey test as part of post Hoc Analysis has been done to assess the significance level. The results are tabulated below under each Knowledge area

Differences in Generational Cohorts responses towards Project Cost Management considering Complexity of the Project

Project Knowledge Areas			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Project Cost Management	Inaccurate Cost estimates	Between Groups	10.597	2	5.299	3.953	.020
		Within Groups	505.285	377	1.340		
		Total	515.882	379			

The above table indicates that Inaccurate cost estimates have a significance value of .020 which is lower than the p value of 0.05. Hence there is a significant impact of this response on project cost performance when considered along with complexity. The below Tukey test shows a high mean of 4.278 for complex projects while a low mean of 3.963 is indicated for complicated projects.

Tukey HSD ^{a,b}			
Project Size(1: Limited and Specific Scope with specific project deliverables ;2- Broader Scope with defined deliverables; 3-Broad and uncertain scope with undefined deliverables)	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
COMPLICATED	162	3.963	
SIMPLE	116	4.009	4.009
COMPLEX	108		4.278
Sig.		.931	.087
Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.			
a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 124.726.			
b. The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.			

FINDINGS

H₀: There is no significant impact on project performance if cost estimates are inaccurate and considering complexity of project

Based on the ANOVA results it is found that there is a significant impact on the project performance of complex projects if the cost estimates are inaccurate. This would impact on project delivery as resource allocation would be constrained. The Tukey tests indicated a high mean for complex projects. The earlier results indicate that complex project fall under the large sized projects which would have a larger concentration of Gen X and Gen Y. Such a situation where resource allocation and lack of team effort impacts delivery, complex projects are bound to fail. Hence it is recommended that managers ensure the cost estimates are done using standard estimation techniques and are buffered sufficiently in order mitigate any unforeseen risks.

H_{3:33}: There is no significant impact on project performance if task estimates are inaccurate and considering complexity of project

Based on the ANOVA and Tukey tests performed, it is found that there is significant impact on the project performance especially in the area of schedule management for complex projects. The earlier results indicate that complex project fall under the large sized projects which would have a larger concentration of Gen X and Gen Y. Such a situation where resource allocation and lack of team effort impacts delivery, complex projects are bound to fail. Hence it is recommended that managers ensure the cost estimates are done using standard estimation techniques and are buffered sufficiently in order mitigate any unforeseen risks.

MANAGING INFLUENCES & COHORT RESPONSE

This generational shift is reshaping organizational profiles to adapt to the different demographics entering the business world. There are research findings which predict that cohort's characteristics and responses may complicate, and potentially disrupt, workplace interactions with members of other generations, thus negatively affecting co-workers and organizational processes.

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This results in conflicts which in turn stimulates uncertainty, aggression and friction in a common work place which in turn result in reduced productivity, innovation.

As the above schematic depicts, each of the project areas are impacted by factors or agents that cause failures which live through the project life cycle starting from Initiation to closure.

CONCLUSION

In general, each generation responds to different management styles, work environments, and motivational techniques which directly affect an employee's overall performance. Managers are developing strategies that from a human perspective are important to identify as the strengths and abilities of the new working generation. These strategies are essential in order to attract and recruit talented individuals whose workplace behavior and social interaction is far different from any previous generation. (Jerome, 2014)

Today's workforce is a combination of multiple generational cohorts who reflect varied behaviors and attitude towards work. With the retirement of many Baby Boomers (1946-1964), the modern workplace is changing and there is a larger influx of workers from the Gen Y and Gen Z cohort joining the already extended Gen X generation cohort. This trend is totally changing the overall workplace landscape and project climate as well. Hence there is a need for modern day project managers to very carefully understand the individual and group behavioral dimensions of the team and derive innovative approaches to deal with multigenerational diversity and related issues.

Organizations have approached diversity issues from a strategic view point but generational diversity which is of a different form, has to be tackled from bottom up approach rather than from a top down approach

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